

Supplementary Information
Design, Synthesis, and Antifungal Analysis of Pyrazoline Derivatives Against
***Candida* Species: A Comprehensive *In Vitro* and *In Silico* Approach**

2-(5-(2-chlorophenyl)-1-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-3-yl)phenol (4a)

UV/vis Spectrum of **4a**

FTIR Spectrum of **4a**

PF-20H-2CL 23 (0.408) Cm (23)

TOF MS ES+
5.07e4

HRMS spectrum of **4a**

^1H NMR of **4a**

2-(5-(3-bromophenyl)-1-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-3-yl)phenol (4b).

UV/vis spectrum of 4b

FTIR spectrum of 4b

HRMS spectrum of 4b

¹H NMR of 4b

3-(3-(2-methoxyphenyl)-1-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-5-yl)phenol (4c)

UV/vis spectrum of 4c

FTIR spectrum of 4c

HRMS spectrum of 4c

¹H NMR of 4c

3-(4-chlorophenyl)-5-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-1-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazole (4d)

FTIR spectrum of 4d

HRMS spectrum of 4d

¹H NMR of 4d

4-(3-(4-fluorophenyl)-5-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)benzenesulfonamide (4e).

FTIR spectrum of 4e

HRMS spectrum of 4d

^1H NMR of 4e